

The general term of the prime number sequence and the Smarandache prime function.

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Let's consider the function $d(i)$ = number of divisors of the positive integer number i . We have found the following expression for this function:

$$d(i) = \sum_{k=1}^i E\left(\frac{i}{k}\right) - E\left(\frac{i-1}{k}\right)$$

We proved this expression in the article "A functional recurrence to obtain the prime numbers using the Smarandache Prime Function".

We deduce that the following function:

$$G(i) = -E\left[-\frac{d(i)-2}{i}\right]$$

This function is called the Smarandache Prime Function (Reference)

It takes the next values:

$$G(i) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } i \text{ is prime} \\ 1 & \text{if } i \text{ is compound} \end{cases}$$

Let us consider now $\pi(n)$ = number of prime numbers smaller or equal than n .

It is simple to prove that:

$$\pi(n) = \sum_{i=2}^n (1 - G(i))$$

Let us have too:

$$\text{If } 1 \leq k \leq p_n - 1 \Rightarrow E\left(\frac{\pi(k)}{n}\right) = 0$$

$$\text{If } C_n \geq k \geq p_n \Rightarrow E\left(\frac{\pi(k)}{n}\right) = 1$$

We will see what conditions have to carry C_n .

Therefore we have the following expression for p_n n -th prime number:

$$p_n = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{C_n} (1 - E\left(\frac{\pi(k)}{n}\right))$$

If we obtain C_n that only depends on n , this expression will be the general term of the prime numbers sequence, since π is in function with G and G does with $d(i)$ that is expressed in function with i too. Therefore the expression only depends on n .

$E[x]$ = The highest integer equal or less than n

Let us consider $C_n = 2(E(n \log n) + 1)$

Since $p_n \sim n \log n$ from a certain n_0 it will be true that

$$(1) \quad p_n \leq 2(E(n \log n) + 1)$$

If n_0 is not too big, we can prove that the inequality is true for smaller or equal values than n_0 .

It is necessary to that:

$$E\left[\frac{\pi(2(E(n \log n) + 1))}{n}\right] = 1$$

If we check the inequality:

$$(2) \quad \pi(2(E(n \log n) + 1)) < 2n$$

We will obtain that:

$$\frac{\pi(C_n)}{n} < 2 \Rightarrow E\left[\frac{\pi(C_n)}{n}\right] \leq 1 \quad ; \quad C_n \geq p_n \Rightarrow E\left[\frac{\pi(C_n)}{n}\right] = 1$$

We can experimentally check this last inequality saying that it checks for a lot of values and the difference tends to increase, which makes to think that it is true for all n .

Therefore if we prove that the next inequalities are true:

$$(1) \quad p_n \leq 2(E(n \log n) + 1)$$

$$(2) \quad \pi(2(E(n \log n) + 1)) < 2n$$

which seems to be very probable; we will have that the general term of the prime numbers sequence is:

$$p_n = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{2(E(n \log n) + 1)} \left[1 - E \left[\frac{\sum_{j=2}^k \left[1 + E \left[\frac{\sum_{s=1}^j (E(\mu_s) - E((j-1)\gamma_s) - 2}{j} \right] \right]}{n} \right] \right]$$

If now we consider the general term defined in the same way but for all real number greater than zero the following graphic is obtained:

Let us observe that if $0 < x < 1$ $P(x)=1$ si $x=1$ $P(x)=2$ and for $n-1 < x \leq n$ $P(x)=p_n$

Reference:

[1] E. Burton, "Smarandache Prime and Coprime Functions"

[Http://www.gallup.unm.edu/~Smarandache/primfct.txt](http://www.gallup.unm.edu/~Smarandache/primfct.txt)

[2] F. Smarandache, "Collected Papers", Vol. II, 200 p., p.137, Kishinev University Press.